

COMPLETE HEART BLOCK SECONDARY TO ANTERIOR MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION PRESENTING AS STOKES-ADAMS SYNDROME: A CASE REPORT

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Abstract

Introduction: Stokes-Adams syndrome, a transient loss of consciousness resulting from cerebral hypoperfusion, is often linked to episodes of significant bradycardia or asystole. It is a clinical manifestation of advanced heart block and is a medical emergency requiring immediate attention.

Case Report: A 60-year-old male with a known history of hypertension presented to the Medical Intensive Care Unit (MICU) after collapsing suddenly at home. The patient had no prior episodes of syncope or significant arrhythmias reported. According to the patient's family, he was walking when he suddenly became unresponsive, with the episode lasting approximately 45 seconds. The patient was alert but appeared fatigued. On investigation, an Electrocardiogram (ECG) showed a 3rd-degree (complete) heart block, a Prolonged PR interval (>300 ms), and Broad QRS complexes suggestive of ventricular escape rhythm. Chest X-ray showed no evidence of pulmonary edema or mediastinal widening and the Echocardiograph showed Moderate hypokinesis of the left ventricular anterior wall with an ejection fraction of 45.0%. The combination of acute myocardial infarction (MI), complete heart block, and the transient loss of consciousness with pallor strongly indicated a Stokes-Adams attack triggered by bradyarrhythmia. The working diagnosis was ACS with a 3rd-degree heart block and a Stokes-Adams episode.

Conclusion: Complete heart block can result from ischemia involving the LAD artery due to its supply to the conduction system. Early revascularization is critical for improving outcomes in ACS with complications such as conduction disturbances.

Keywords: Stokes-Adams syndrome, Acute Coronary Syndrome, Loss of consciousness

Introduction:

Acute coronary syndrome (ACS) is a spectrum of clinical conditions ranging from unstable angina to myocardial infarction, resulting from acute ischemia of the myocardium due to coronary artery obstruction¹. The occurrence of ACS in conjunction with a 3rd-degree heart block signifies a severe disruption in cardiac

electrical conduction, often leading to significant hemodynamic compromise. One of the alarming complications of such bradyarrhythmias is a Stokes-Adams attack, characterized by transient loss of consciousness caused by cerebral hypoperfusion. This condition represents a medical emergency that requires prompt diagnosis and treatment to prevent life-threatening outcomes².

Stokes-Adams syndrome is an abrupt, transient loss of consciousness due to a sudden but pronounced decrease in cardiac output, caused by a paroxysmal shift in the heartbeat's mechanism. Most patients have complete heart block, with ventricular irritability or asystole during syncopal attacks, but both supraventricular and ventricular tachyarrhythmias without atrioventricular (A-V) block may be the responsible mechanism. Multiple different arrhythmias may produce Stokes-Adams syncope in the same patient³⁻⁵.

The condition represents a medical emergency that requires prompt diagnosis and treatment to prevent life-threatening outcomes⁶. This case report highlights the clinical presentation, diagnostic challenges, and therapeutic interventions for a patient with this rare but critical combination of ACS, complete heart block, and Stokes-Adams syndrome, emphasizing the importance of a multidisciplinary approach in managing complex cardiovascular emergencies.

Case Presentation

A 60-year-old male with a known history of hypertension presented to the Medical Intensive Care Unit (MICU) after collapsing suddenly at home. The patient had no prior episodes of syncope or significant arrhythmias reported. According to the patient's family, he was walking when he suddenly became unresponsive, with the episode lasting approximately 45 seconds. There were no preceding symptoms such as chest pain, palpitations, dizziness, or shortness of breath. During the unresponsive period, he appeared pale and pulseless. Upon spontaneous recovery, the patient experienced severe chest discomfort and profound fatigue but denied any confusion or neurological deficits. This was his first such episode. Regarding the Past Medical History, Hypertension was well-controlled with amlodipine, no known coronary artery disease or arrhythmias, and non-smoker, occasional alcohol use. On arrival at the MICU: The patient was alert but appeared fatigued. Vital Signs: Blood pressure: 90/60 mmHg; heart rate: 57 beats per minute (bradycardic); respiratory rate: 18 breaths per minute; oxygen saturation: 98% on room air. On Cardiovascular Examination: Distant heart sounds were noted. No murmurs, gallops, or rubs were appreciated. Peripheral pulses were weak but palpable. On Neurological Examination: Intact cranial nerves, motor strength, and reflexes. No focal deficits were observed. Respiratory Examination: Clear bilateral breath sounds with no signs of pulmonary congestion.

On Investigation, an Electrocardiogram (ECG) showed a 3rd-degree (complete) heart block, a Prolonged PR interval (>300 ms), and Broad QRS complexes suggestive of ventricular escape rhythm. Laboratory investigations showed an elevated cardiac troponin I: 2.1 ng/mL (reference: <0.04 ng/mL), Normal electrolytes, renal function, and complete blood count and B-type natriuretic peptide (BNP): 480 pg/mL, indicating cardiac strain. Chest X-ray showed no evidence of pulmonary edema or mediastinal widening and the Echocardiograph showed Moderate hypokinesis of the left ventricular anterior wall with an ejection fraction of 45.0%. The combination of acute myocardial infarction (MI), complete heart block, and the transient loss of consciousness

with pallor strongly indicated a Stokes-Adams attack triggered by bradyarrhythmia. The working diagnosis was ACS with a 3rd-degree heart block and a Stokes-Adams episode.

Figure 1: ECG showing a 3rd-degree (complete) heart block, a Prolonged PR interval (>300 ms), and Broad QRS complexes

Management of the case:

Initial stabilization involved administering intravenous fluids to improve perfusion and support blood pressure, applying transcutaneous pacing pads as a precautionary measure, and initiating continuous ECG monitoring. Definitive interventions included coronary angiography, which revealed a critical occlusion of the left anterior descending (LAD) artery, followed by immediate percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) with drug-eluting stent placement, and the implantation of a dual-chamber permanent pacemaker to address the complete heart block. Adjunctive medical therapy comprised dual antiplatelet therapy with aspirin and clopidogrel, anticoagulation with low molecular weight heparin during hospitalization, high-intensity statin therapy with atorvastatin 80 mg daily, and the cautious introduction of beta-blockers and ACE inhibitors post-procedure.

Outcome& Follow-up: The patient's hemodynamic status improved significantly following PCI and pacemaker implantation. He reported resolution of chest pain and demonstrated a stable heart rate and rhythm. The troponin levels trended downward, and follow-up echocardiography showed improved left ventricular function. The

patient was discharged on day five with clear instructions for lifestyle modifications and medication adherence. Scheduled outpatient follow-up with cardiology for pacemaker checks and cardiac rehabilitation.

Discussion:

Stokes-Adams syndrome refers to a sudden and temporary loss of consciousness caused by a sharp reduction in cardiac output due to an abrupt change in the heart's rhythm^{7,8}. This condition is most often associated with complete heart block, where ventricular asystole or irritability leads to syncopal episodes. However, other arrhythmias, including supraventricular and ventricular tachyarrhythmias without atrioventricular (A-V) block, can also trigger these episodes. In some cases, a single patient may experience Stokes-Adams syncope caused by multiple types of arrhythmias. Advances in continuous cardiac monitoring and the development of sophisticated electrical pacemakers have significantly enhanced both the diagnosis and management of this condition⁹.

Complete heart block is a rare but severe complication of ACS, often associated with inferior wall MI due to ischemia of the AV node. However, this case involved an anterior wall MI with LAD occlusion. The transient loss of consciousness, known as a Stokes-Adams attack, underscores the urgency of intervention in bradyarrhythmia's. The use of coronary revascularization and permanent pacing highlights the importance of a timely and multidisciplinary approach in managing such critical presentations.

A complete heart block (3rd-degree AV block), with a prolonged PR interval (>300 ms) and broad QRS complexes indicative of a ventricular escape rhythm. This bradyarrhythmia is a common culprit for Stokes-Adams attacks. Elevated cardiac troponin I (2.1 ng/mL) indicated myocardial injury consistent with acute coronary syndrome. Echocardiography: Moderate hypokinesis of the left ventricular anterior wall and an ejection fraction (EF) of 45% pointed to left ventricular dysfunction likely resulting from ischemia in the territory of the left anterior descending (LAD) artery. Chest X-ray: Normal findings ruled out significant pulmonary congestion or mediastinal pathology. On laboratory investigations, normal renal function, electrolytes, and complete blood count were excluded as secondary contributors to bradyarrhythmia. However, an elevated B-type natriuretic peptide (BNP) of 480 pg/mL confirmed cardiac strain.

In the present study, there was a transient loss of consciousness for 45 seconds was reported. Arcuri et al¹⁰ study also reported an apparent loss of consciousness for 55 seconds. In this study, a complete heart block (3rd-degree AV block), with a prolonged PR interval (>300 ms) and broad QRS complexes indicative of a ventricular escape rhythm. In Clarke et al¹¹ study series, only one of the three patients with complete AV block presented with an Adams-Stokes attack, and Carano N et al¹² study reported a high degree of complete AV block, with periods of asystole longer than five seconds.

Conclusion:

This case illustrates the complex interplay between ACS, bradyarrhythmia, and Stokes-Adams syndrome. Complete heart block can result from ischemia involving the LAD artery due to its supply to the conduction system. Early revascularization is critical for improving outcomes in ACS with complications such as conduction disturbances. Permanent pacing is essential in cases of persistent bradyarrhythmia's to prevent the recurrence of syncopal episodes and sudden cardiac death. Early recognition, prompt intervention, and comprehensive follow-up are essential to ensure favourable outcomes in such life-threatening conditions.

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